

EFFICACY OF KARANJA, KASISA, KAPITTHA, MADYANTIKA, AMLA, BHRUNGRAJ IN PALITYA (GREYING OF HAIR/ALBINISM)**Dr. Deodatta Bhadlikar¹, Dr. Devyani Bhadlikar², Dr. Shruti Saxena*³, Dr. Archana Pandey Jumle⁴, Rahul Jumle⁵**

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INTRODUCTION

Now a days people use many cosmetics, dye's for colouring. Since the drawbacks of modern medicines results in greying, skin reaction, hair fall, without permanent effects and with several side effects, there is an utmost need of non toxic, non irritant herbal Ayurvedic products for colouration.

Facts regarding grey Hair

- Normally by the age of 35 hair start growing grey.
- In Leucoderma the hair remains white as long as Leucoderma lasts.
- Decrease in formation or a kind of blockage in the chemical process of formation of melanin a colouring pigment present at the hair root leads to formation of grey hair.
- Rapid greying of hair may occur after emotional stress in certain internal diseases.
- Chemically the human scalp has acidic reaction varying between PH 4.5 to 5.5 due to lactic acid secretion.
- Greying of hair cannot occur overnight.

- Chemical contents of hair is cystine, cysteine, sulphur, and nitrotyrosine found in male hair than female hair.
- Plucking of grey hair leads to dislocation of melanin present in the neighbouring hair, which may lead to more grey hair.

AIM

To see the efficacy of Karanja, Kasisa, Kapittha, Madhatika, Amla and Bhrungraj in Palitya (Greying of Hair/Albinism).

AYURVEDIC VIEW - GREYING OF HAIR

- Hair is a mirror of body.
- Hair is paternal constituent.
- Sushruta says Vata dosha imparts black colour to hair.
- Premature greying is attributed to the deranged Rasa dhatu.
- Healthy condition of hair depends upon healthy Asthidhatu.

MATERIALS

- 20 patients were selected between age group 5 to 50 years of both sexes.
 - Anti Greying Lepa
 - Leaf of pongmia glabra (Karanja)
 - Ripe fruit of Ferronia elephantum (Kapittha)
 - Ferrous sulphate $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Kasisa)
 - Leaf of Lawsonia inermis (Madyantica)
 - Fruit of Emblica officinalis (Amla)
 - Eclipta Alba (Bhrungraj)
- in equal qty.
- in double qty

METHODS / TRIAL PROCEDURE

- In above mention proportion of Anti greying Lepa, water was added in double the quantity. It was soaked over night, boiled it in the morning by giving moderate heat, till paste of ingredients was formed. 1/4th thick angul lepa was applied on affected part, two times i.e. morning and evening per day till it dries off on the scalp.
- The oral administration of Ajasthi Bhasma (Burnt ash of Goat bone) 125 mg two times and Tab. Bhrungraj Gharivati 2 tabs two time after for per day was given.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

- Inspection, palpation and interrogation.
- General and Local examination.
- Examination of 'Asthivaha strotasa' and 'Asthidhatu' status.
- Haemoglobin percentage of each and every patient was determined.

ASSESSMENT OF EFFICACY

The efficacy was assessed on every 30th day follow up for 6 months on the basis of following criteria:

- The colour changing effect.
- Arrest of new grey hair.
- Screening of patient.
- Arrest of hair fall and regeneration of hair was also assessed on every 30th day follow up for 6 months in this clinical study.
- The assessment of therapeutic effect is made on four point scale.

OBSERVATION

- The maximum number (70%) of patient were of madhama - avastha.
- Male were more affected than female. (60%)
- Deha prakriti plays an important role in developing Palitya. The maximum number of patient were of Pitta Prakriti than any other Prakriti i.e. 50%.
- Equal history of dye user and non user were found.
- The average frequency of grey hair in 20 patients of Palitya were 209 hair. that means average 10 grey hair per 25 mm² area.

RESULTS

In the clinical study of Anti greying lepa in 20 patients of greying the efficacy was as follows:

- Colour changing effect was 90%
- Arresting greying of hair was 70%.
- And also the efficacy seen in arresting hair fall was 100% in 10 pts and 84% in remaining 10 pts. Hereditary factor, anaemia, psychologic factor plays an important role in developing Palitya (greying of hair).

RESULT OF ANTI GREYING LEPA

BHRUNGARAJ
(*Eclipta Alba*)

AMLA
(Fruit of *Emblica Officinalis*)

MADYANTICA
(Leaf of *Lawsonia Inermis*)

KARANJA
(*Pongamia glabra*)

KAPPITTHA
(*Feronia elephantum*)

KASISA
($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$)

OBSERVATION**THE ROLE OF AGE IN 20 CASES OF 'PALITYA' (GREYING OF HAIR)**

The maximum number (70%) of patients were of 'Madhyam-awastha'

THE ROLE OF SEX IN 20 CASES OF 'PALITYA' (GREYING OF HAIR)

Male were more affected than female.

THE DISTRIBUTION OF 'DEHA PRAKRITI' IN 20 CASES OF 'PALITYA' (GREYING OF HAIR)

'Deha Prakriti' plays an important role in developing 'palitya'. The maximum number of patients were of 'Pitta Prakriti' than any other 'Prakriti' i.e. 50%.

THE STUDY OF DYE USERS ON SCALP FOUND IN 20 CASES OF 'PALITYA' (GREYING OF HAIR)

Equal history of dye user and non user were found.

THE DISTRIBUTION OF GREY HAIR IN SCATTERED PATTERN IN 25 MM² AREA

Sr. No. of Patients	No. of Grey Hair	Sr. No. of Patients	No. of Grey Hair
01	4	11	1
02	2	12	25
03	5	13	10
04	15	14	2
05	26	15	9
06	30	16	14
07	22	17	12
08	5	18	10
09	5	19	6
10	3	20	3
Total No. of Grey Hair			209

The average frequency of grey hair in 20 patients of Palitya were 209 hair, that means average '10' grey hair per 25 mm² area.

CONCLUSION

- The colour changing effect, arrest of new grey, hair screening of patients showed significant results and marked improvement.
- It is also effective in arresting hair fall and regeneration of hair.
- The preparation of antigreying lepa being cheap, easy to prepare, effective, potent and without side effect, it is concluded that, the Anti greying lepa is good in initial stage of Palitya (Greying of hair).